

EBFMC25-OP-69 · Evaluation of General Attitudes of Assistant Physicians Towards Artificial Intelligence

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Artificial intelligence (AI) has become increasingly significant in the healthcare sector, offering advancements in diagnostics, treatment planning, and patient management. Understanding physicians' perspectives on AI is crucial for its successful integration into medical practice. This study aims to assess assistant physicians' awareness, acceptance, and concerns regarding AI, highlighting their knowledge levels, willingness to adopt AI technologies, and ethical considerations.

Materials and Methods: A descriptive, cross-sectional survey was conducted among assistant physicians from various specialties. Data were collected through an online questionnaire via Google Forms, comprising a sociodemographic section and the General Attitudes Toward Artificial Intelligence Scale. This scale was originally developed by Schepman and Rodway (2020) and later adapted into Turkish by Kaya et al. (2022). Statistical analyses were performed to evaluate trends in AI perception and acceptance.

Results: Among the participants, 54.8% are male, 57.3% are married, and the majority (78.3%) work in internal medical sciences. While 37.6% have been practicing medicine for more than six years, 36.3% have been working as residents for over two years.

A total of 45.9% reported possessing fundamental knowledge of artificial intelligence (AI), whereas 29.9% indicated familiarity with AI technologies. The proportion of individuals incorporating AI into their daily lives is 42%, while its professional utilization stands at 30.6%. AI is predominantly employed for information acquisition (80.3%), knowledge updating (42.6%), and patient assessment processes.

Regarding perceptions of AI, 56.1% of participants believe it offers beneficial applications, and 48.4% perceive it as an exciting innovation. However, 29.3% consider AI to pose potential dangers, while 43.9% express concerns about ethical risks associated with its use. Additionally, 18.5% speculate that AI might eventually surpass human control.

Conclusion: Assistant physicians generally demonstrate a positive attitude towards AI, yet concerns persist regarding its ethical implications and potential risks. The application of AI in healthcare is expected to enhance early disease detection and optimize treatment efficiency, thereby contributing to the sustainability of healthcare services. Supporting positive perceptions of AI and encouraging its effective use in medical practice are essential. Increased AI education and awareness programs can help address ethical concerns and ensure that AI technologies are integrated safely and effectively into clinical settings. Additionally, the findings of this study may serve as a foundation for future research and contribute to the development of policies that facilitate AI adoption in healthcare.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Artificial intelligence, physicians' attitude, ethics

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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